

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

USE OF DIGITAL PRODUCTS IN THE TOURISM SECTOR OF GEORGIA (CASE OF ADJARA REGION)

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Abstract

The paper is an integral part of the project "Research on the use of digital products in the Georgian tourism sector" which won the internal grant projects competition of Grigol Robakidze University.

The use of digital products plays an important role in the tourism industry and is a big challenge for a country like Georgia. The need for transformation is particularly important in the field of tourism, where most processes are automated and tailored to the needs and requirements of the customer and/or service provider. The given article aims to overview the digital products that are used by the tourist agencies and hotels in Adjara region of Georgia, to identify international technologies that are spread among the Adjarian hospitality stakeholders and whether Georgian digital products are used or not.

Keywords: Digital Products, Hospitality Industry, Tourism Sector.

Introduction

Most of the companies around the world are involved in the process of digital transformation, which may be painful and financially difficult for some of them, but in the conditions of constant change and development, they cannot exist otherwise. Those employed in the hospitality sector could use this time to develop their businesses by improving their digital tourism services: in our simplified, full-of-choices modern times, only properly marketed businesses survive.

Ajaria is considered one of the best places for holiday stay in the territory of Georgia. Beautiful nature, subtropical climate and splendid sea will guarantee an energy boost here to last for the whole year. Adjara's economy is progressing even faster as compared to the country's economy, its expected growth rate being about 18.5%. While high dependence on tourism, most naturally, made the region more vulnerable the downturn in 2020, the speed of recovery is seen as remarkable.

More than half of Adjara's economy is related to the tourism industry, with HORECA, other tourism services and RE transactions accounting for 35%. The number of trips that brought foreign visitors to the locality reached 333,848 between January-March 2023, marking a 93 percent increase year-on-year and a 33 percent rise compared to the pre-pandemic figures from 2019.

The Department of Tourism and Resorts of Ajara Autonomous Republic is a governmental organization supporting tourism development in Ajara region. It ensures the popularization of the region as a tourist destination on a national and international levels, identification, diversification and development of tourist products and improvement of the service level in the region.

In 2023 it was organized press tours hosting media professionals from various countries to promote the re-

gion. About 500 journalists, bloggers and representatives from tourism agencies visited Adjara as part of the promotional campaigns. Batumi was hosting many international events, a fact would make a positive impact on increasing the number of tourists in the region.

EarthPix, a major American travel platform, is promoting Georgia's Black Sea city of Batumi to millions of its subscribers in a new promotional campaign by the region's Tourism Department. The followers of the platform had seen a video about the popular statues of Ali and Nino, two historical figures, that has become an iconic sign of the seaside city.

Domestic tourism promotional campaign - Follow Me in Adjara, implemented by the Adjara Tourism Department for the first time this year, reached over 100 million hits on social media platforms.

According to Meladze et al. (2023) digital technologies, was completely changed the lifestyle of travelers. Travelers nowadays are not booking tickets or hotels at travel agencies as they were doing it before. They prefer to plan everything on their own, as in some cases it is cheaper and also it makes traveling more flexible, customer orientated. Georgian digital apps market will offer web-site or mobile application, which will give possibility to book all hotels in Georgia, as it is booking.com or Airbnb, it can have a positive future.

Digital products play a significant role in transforming the hospitality industry, enhancing customer experiences, improving operational efficiency, and increasing revenue.

Desk research

According to the secondary research, conducted using scientific articles, research papers, literature reviews as well as books of Georgian and foreign scientists and relevant web-pages, these are the most widely spread digital product categories in the hospitality sector:

- **Online Booking Systems** (Booking Platforms as Websites and Mobile apps that allow customers to

book rooms, tables, or services online and Channel Managers that help hotels manage inventory and bookings across various online platforms;

- **Mobile Apps** (Hotel Apps to provide guests with a seamless experience, allowing them to check-in, access room keys, order room service, and explore local attractions and Restaurant Apps to enable customers to view menus, place orders, and make reservations);

- **Property Management Systems** (Cloud-Based PMS to streamline hotel operations, including reservation management, check-in/check-out processes, and billing);

- **Customer Relationship Management** (CRM Systems to manage guest information, preferences, and interactions to personalize services and improve guest loyalty);

- **Digital Concierge Services** (Chatbots and Virtual Assistants that provide real-time information, recommendations, and assistance to guests);

- **In-Room Technology** (Smart Room Controls to allow guests to control lighting, temperature, and entertainment systems through mobile apps or in-room tablets and Voice-Activated Assistants which enhance guest experience by enabling voice commands for various services);

- **Payment Solutions** (Digital Wallets allow seamless and secure transactions and Mobile Payments enabling guests to pay for services using their mobile devices);

- **Guest Feedback and Review Platforms** (Feedback Apps to collect guest reviews and feedback to improve services and address concerns promptly);

- **Data Analytics and Business Intelligence** (Analytics Tools: Help hotels and restaurants analyze data to make informed decisions, such as pricing strategies and marketing efforts);

- **Wi-Fi and Connectivity Solutions** (High-Speed Wi-Fi: Essential for guest satisfaction and for business travelers who need a reliable internet connection);

- **Online Training and Employee Management** (Training Platforms: Ensure that staff is well-trained in hospitality standards and Employee Scheduling Software: Optimize staff schedules for efficient operations);

- **Digital Marketing Tools** (Social Media Management: Enhance online presence and engage with customers and Email Marketing Platforms: Keep guests informed about promotions, events, and updates);

- **Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR):** Virtual Tours: Provide virtual previews of rooms and facilities to potential guests and AR Applications: Enhance on-site experiences through interactive elements;

- **Environmental Monitoring and Sustainability Tools** (Energy Management Systems to monitor and control energy usage to reduce costs and environmental impact and Sustainability Apps to educate guests about the hotel's eco-friendly practices).

The integration of these digital products allows hospitality businesses to streamline operations, personalize guest experiences, and stay competitive in a rapidly evolving industry.

Qualitative research results

During the research a qualitative method was used to obtain information about attitudes towards digital technologies (structured questionnaires were developed).

Regarding the research into the adoption of digital products within the tourism industry, the study involved the participation of 12 tour companies and 27 hotels situated in the Adjara region, recognized as Europe's Leading All-season destination. Tourist companies predominantly utilize globally recognized digital products, with international acclaim, as their primary tools:

- For collecting information about the customers: Travel Platforms, Social Media, Messenger, E-Mail, WhatsApp, Telegram;

- For booking and purchasing tickets: Amadeus, Omio, Expedia, Skyscanner, also Georgian digital products: Railway.ge, Georgianbus.ge, Tkt.ge, Matarebeli.ge;

- For hotel reservations and check-ins: Rate Hawk, Booking.com, Airbnb.com, e-mail, Area.ly.

- For payment: Bank Transfers, Internet Banking, POS Terminal;

- For feedback to the customers: WhatsApp, Messenger, Skype, Telegram, social media platforms;

In addition to the aforementioned international tools, findings indicate the utilization of digital products developed in Georgia, such as self.ge, retain.ge, biliki.ge, area.ly, travelgis.ge, LiveCaller.io, wifisher.com, Fina, FMG, Tripcamp.ge and Oris.

Regarding digital tools within hotels, the following products are employed:

- Otelms.com, Fina, Oracle Fidelio, Little Hotelier, TravelLine, telephone, and internet to collect information about customers;

- Otelms.com, Booking.com, Fidelio, Opera PMS, and telephone for reservations and purchases;

- Opera, Otelms.com, Wi-Fi as digital in-room technologies;

- Micros, Otelms.com as digital technologies for F&B services;

- POS terminal, Opera Pms, online bank, bank transfer, Micros / Symphony, Fina, smart invoicing for payments;

- Micros, Otelms.Com. Book4time, Micros for spa and fitness services;

- Telephone, outlook, Medallica, Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, Otelms.Com, Booking.Com, Traveline, Revinate, GXP, e-mail for customer feedback;

- Georgian digital products used in the hotels are: self.ge, retain.ge, biliki.ge, area.ly, travelgis.ge, LiveCaller.io, wifisher.com, Fina, FMG, Tripcamp.ge and Oris.

According to the research findings, both tourist agencies and hotels have integrated digital products from both international and Georgian sources into their operations.

Utilizing both international and Georgian digital products in hospitality operations is important for several reasons: **International products** often bring a wealth of features and capabilities developed through global perspectives and experiences; they can enhance

the competitiveness of hospitality businesses on a global scale, meeting the expectations of diverse international guests; international products may have a broader appeal, accommodating the cultural diversity of guests from various parts of the world and can contribute to global economic networks, facilitating cross-border collaborations. **Georgian products** offer unique features tailored to the local market and cultural preferences, Georgian products allow businesses to showcase local innovation and cater to specific regional needs; Georgian digital products can contribute to a sense of local authenticity and resonate better with domestic customers; adopting Georgian digital products supports the local tech industry, fostering economic growth and innovation within the country. The combined use of international and Georgian digital products in hospitality operations allows businesses to leverage global standards, meet local needs, and create a well-rounded and adaptable digital infrastructure.

Conclusions

In summary, it can be affirmed that tourism agencies and hotels in the Adjara region not only employ established digital products (Amadeus, Omio, Expedia, Skyscanner, Booking.com, Airbnb.com) but also incorporate technologies from local Georgian providers (self.ge, retain.ge, biliki.ge, area.ly, travelgis.ge, Live-Caller.io, wifisher.com, Fina, FMG, Tripcamp.ge and Oris) which enables a balance between embracing global trends and supporting the local ecosystem.

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